

From Event to Artefact: In-Class and Live-Streamed Guest Lectures with AI-supported Review

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Abstract

Large classes make guest lectures simultaneously attractive and fragile: they can add authenticity and professional visibility, yet access, interaction, and post-lecture consolidation are difficult to sustain at scale. This paper reports a guest lecture design embedded in a 12-week postgraduate project management module enrolling 284 business school students. Four practitioner sessions (2 hours, including moderated Q&A) were delivered as Zoom-enabled events: one speaker joined remotely; three were delivered on campus while live-streamed and recorded. Recordings were posted to the virtual learning environment with AI-generated transcripts and summary notes, lightly edited to correct obvious errors, and students completed a low-stakes end-of-module reflection where guest-lecture insights could be integrated. A post-series survey indicates strong uptake of recordings and substantial perceived value of AI artefacts for review and reflection, alongside a consistent social presence trade-off for remote delivery. Design implications are offered for inclusive, sustainable guest-lecture pedagogy in large classes.

Keywords: *Guest lectures; large-class pedagogy; AI-generated transcripts; HyFlex-like delivery; technology-enhanced learning.*

1. Introduction

Large classes are no longer exceptional in higher education. Massification has expanded access but has also made interaction, participation, and feedback harder to sustain at scale (Hornsby & Osman, 2014; Mulryan-Kyne, 2010). This creates a familiar tension for professional programmes. Guest lectures can bring professional practice into the curriculum, but in large cohorts authenticity is harder to realise pedagogically because opportunities for students to ask follow-up questions, receive acknowledgement, and test ideas publicly are necessarily limited. What might feel dialogic and memorable in a small cohort can therefore become primarily observational at scale unless access, participation pathways, and post-event reuse are deliberately designed. In this sense, large-class conditions compress interaction, distribute attention across many students, and make later consolidation more dependent on explicit design.

Two developments have made this design more feasible. Zoom now enables live-streamed guest lectures with recordings for later access, in ways that align broadly with hybrid-flexible (HyFlex) research on multimodal participation and access (Barr & Luo, 2025; Yang et al., 2025). Platforms can also generate AI transcripts and notes, making it easier for students to search and review lecture content afterwards. However, mediated delivery can weaken social presence and participation (Richardson et al., 2017) and AI summaries may encourage more superficial engagement if they are used in place of active learning (Corbin & Walton, 2025).

This paper examines a large-class guest lecture approach organised around three stages: equitable access, interaction during the session, and consolidation afterwards. Zoom was used to livestream and record all guest lecture events; recordings were posted to the virtual learning environment with AI transcripts and summary notes; and students completed a low-stakes end-of-module reflection where they were encouraged to integrate “lessons learned” from guest lectures. The paper asks two practice-focused questions:

- What trade-offs arise in engagement and perceived connection when guest lectures are mediated through Zoom in a large class?
- How do students perceive AI-generated transcripts and summary notes as supports for review and reflection, and what design moves increase their pedagogical value at scale?

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

The case is a 12-week postgraduate (5-credit) project management module in a business school enrolling 284 students drawn from four taught MSc programmes. The module was primarily delivered in person. The only “hybridised” component was the guest lecture

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series, which was implemented as Zoom-enabled events to improve access and to create reusable learning artefacts.

2.1. Guest lecture series and event format

Four practitioners from different organisations contributed guest lectures. For reporting purposes, speakers are described by sector and role:

- a humanitarian organisation leader (director level) responsible for international partnerships (remote delivery via Zoom due to speaker location on-the-ground),
- a professional services consulting leader (director level) (delivered on campus),
- a public-sector leader (CEO level) (delivered on campus), and
- a professional services leader (senior manager level) (delivered on campus).

Each session ran for 2 hours, including discussion and Q&A. All sessions followed a consistent large-class facilitation format:

- Students attended in a lecture theatre with a parallel Zoom livestream for students who could not attend on campus.
- Q&A was moderated by two or three module lecturers. In-room questions were facilitated in the theatre; online questions were monitored in Zoom during the session and integrated into discussion in real time.
- Two room cameras and Zoom display allowed online participants to see the speaker and the audience of the lecture theatre, with the view controlled by a facilitator during the session.
- Each session was recorded in Zoom and made available to the full cohort after the event.

This design is consistent with the “equivalency and reusability” principles often emphasised in HyFlex research: students should be able to engage meaningfully across modes and benefit from reusable artefacts (Barr & Luo, 2025; Beatty, 2019).

2.2. AI transcripts and summary notes for post-lecture review

After each guest lecture, the Zoom recording link was posted to the module’s virtual learning environment. Each recording included:

- an AI-generated transcript, and
- AI-generated summary notes.

To improve usability and trust, transcripts and notes were lightly edited using platform functionality (e.g., correcting obvious misrecognitions, terminology, and formatting). This is not a claim of “perfect accuracy.” Rather, it is a pragmatic human-in-the-loop approach motivated by evidence that automatic speech recognition performance can vary

substantially across vendors and conditions, with streaming settings posing particular challenges (Kuhn et al., 2023).

Transcripts and summary notes were intended to support students in three main ways:

- enable review and retrieval (searching and locating specific concepts and examples),
- support reflection and consolidation after the live event, and
- enhance inclusion and flexibility, especially for students balancing work or commuting constraints and for students who benefit from pacing controls and repeat access (Horlin et al., 2024; Wang, 2024).

2.3. Low-stakes reflection as integration

Guest lectures were integrated through a low-stakes reflective component at the end of the module. Students completed a short reflection as part of a broader reflective assignment and were encouraged to incorporate “lessons learned” from guest lectures where relevant. This design aimed to help students move from exposure to integration, using reflection to select, interpret, and connect guest lecture insights to module concepts. Reflective activities are widely used in professional education, but the evidence base suggests that their value depends on how reflection is structured and supported in practice (Mann et al., 2009).

3. Literature Review

3.1. Large classes: moving from size to design

Large classes can constrain interaction and participation, but the issue is not size as a purely numerical attribute. Rather, the literature suggests that scale changes the practical conditions of teaching and learning: opportunities for individual contribution become scarcer, monitoring understanding in real time becomes more difficult, and pedagogical choices must remain feasible within constraints of time, space, and workload (Hornsby & Osman, 2014; Mulryan-Kyne, 2010). In parallel, active learning research consistently indicates that students benefit when they engage cognitively and behaviourally with ideas rather than only receiving information (Freeman et al., 2014; Prince, 2004), though implementing such approaches at scale is not straightforward. This is especially relevant for guest lectures. They are often valued for the authenticity and professional visibility they can bring to a module, yet in large classes they can easily remain presentation-led unless questioning, interaction, and follow-up are deliberately structured. This challenge also aligns with work on experiential learning and networked teaching in business education, which shows that active and applied approaches are harder to enact at scale and require more distributed pedagogical coordination and careful attention to the student experience

(Huber, 2023; Mantai & Huber, 2021). The pedagogical question therefore concerns how guest lectures can be designed so that authenticity is converted into equitable access, credible interaction, and later consolidation without creating an unsustainable burden..

3.2. Social presence and engagement in mediated sessions

Social presence, the sense of “realness” and connection with others in mediated environments, has a strong and consistent relationship with student satisfaction and perceived learning in online settings (Richardson et al., 2017). This perspective is important for Zoom-enabled guest lectures because even strong content may be received differently when the speaker is physically absent and interaction cues are reduced. For large classes, where interaction is already scarce, mediated delivery can shift the experience toward ‘broadcast’ unless the session is deliberately structured for participation and a sense of class community (Farrell, 2022; Gao, 2021). Research related to HyFlex reinforces this design point: providing multiple participation pathways can increase access, but equivalency across modes is not automatic; interaction, classroom climate, and facilitation choices shape how students experience the different modalities (Barr & Luo, 2025; Yang et al., 2025).

3.3. Lecture capture, transcripts, and inclusive access

Lecture capture has become an increasingly mainstream part of higher education learning infrastructure. Systematic mapping work shows that student usage patterns are heterogeneous and that recordings can shape study behaviours in both positive and negative ways (Banerjee, 2021). Recent empirical studies suggest that captions and transcripts can improve students’ perceptions of lecture capture and provide a searchable resource for consolidation, though the benefits depend on how these features are integrated and whether students use them strategically (Dommett et al., 2022).

Importantly for large classes, the strongest pedagogical argument for recordings and transcripts is increasingly framed in terms of inclusion rather than convenience. Studies of lecture recording in UK higher education highlight its role in promoting inclusive access, particularly by enabling students to manage pace, revisit content, and reduce barriers created by time-and-place constraints (Wang, 2024). Research with neurodivergent and disabled students similarly emphasises that recordings can be essential for participation and that “functional flexibility” (pause, speed control, repeated access) supports self-regulated learning (Horlin et al., 2024). These findings align with large-class realities: if guest lectures are part of the intended learning experience, scalable access mechanisms are not necessarily optional.

3.4. Generative AI, transcripts, and risks of superficial engagement

The rapid diffusion of generative AI tools has reshaped higher education discussions around teaching, learning, and academic support, with growing uptake among both staff and students (Lee et al., 2024; O’Dea, 2024). Student-facing evidence indicates widespread engagement with AI chatbots in higher education, alongside significant variation in student attitudes and concerns (Stöhr et al., 2024). In this context, AI-generated summaries and transcripts are attractive because they appear to reduce both cognitive and practical burdens, where ‘everything is captured’. However, emerging critique warns that AI summarisation may reduce depth of engagement when students rely on summaries in place of reading, listening, or active processing (Corbin & Walton, 2025). This is consistent with broader evidence that learning is harmed when note-taking becomes mere transcription rather than generative processing (Mueller & Oppenheimer, 2014). Applied to guest lectures, the design challenge therefore concerns how AI transcripts are framed: as drafts that support retrieval and reflection, rather than as authoritative replacements for listening, questioning, and synthesis..

4. Empirical Methodology/Data

4.1. Survey administration and ethics

Evaluation data were collected via an anonymous post-series survey administered after all four guest lectures were completed. The survey was facilitated by an independent staff member not involved in the module, to reduce social desirability bias and any perceived pressure to respond. Students could rate all four guest lectures because all recordings were available in the virtual learning environment. A total of 122 responses were recorded from a cohort of 284 (43% response rate). Item-level response counts vary because some questions were optional or conditional. Ethical approval was granted by the University Research Ethics Committee to research student learning and engagement preferences (Ref: 2024/213).

4.2. Measures and analysis approach

Survey items captured:

- preferred learning format (in-person vs online),
- live attendance and recording use per lecture,
- perceived engagement and value of the guest lectures,
- perceived impact of delivery mode on engagement and connection, and
- perceived usefulness and uptake of AI transcripts and summary notes.

Referring to Table 1, analysis in this paper is descriptive, reporting frequencies and percentages to characterise perceptions at scale. Open-text responses were reviewed to identify high-level issues about transcript usefulness and limitations.

Table 1. Headline survey indicators.

Indicator	Result (descriptive)	Item n
Typical learning format preference	84% prefer in-person; 9% online; 7% no preference	97
Live attendance (per lecture)	68-84% reported attending live	94
Recorded viewing (per lecture)	51-66% reported viewing recordings	77
Respondents rating engagement as very or extremely high	Remote lecture: 49% rated engagement as very/extremely high; in-person lectures (pooled): 56%	95
Mode effect on engagement	66% engaged more in person; 20% no difference; 5% more via Zoom	91
Connection with remote speaker	49% weaker; 22% same; 29% stronger (vs in-person guest lectures)	91
AI transcripts/summary usefulness	55% very/extremely useful; 23% unaware/did not use	91
Transcripts support review/reflection	48% very/extremely; 28% moderately	90
Transcripts as substitute for note-taking	57% probably/definitely yes; 27% not sure	90
Preferred future guest lecture context	69% prefer a combination of contexts	89

5. Analysis of/Reflection on/Implications for Practice

5.1. Access, reuse, and inclusion

Across all sessions, a substantial proportion of respondents reported live attendance and a large proportion reported watching recordings. In a cohort of 284, this dual pattern supports inclusion. The literature on lecture recording increasingly frames access as part of inclusive

practice, enabling students to manage pace, revisit dense content, and reduce attendance penalties associated with commuting and work constraints (Horlin et al., 2024; Wang, 2024).

For guest lectures, reusability is important because the learning value often lies in nuanced examples and professional judgement that are difficult to reconstruct from memory. Recordings allow students to return to these examples during consolidation. At the same time, lecture capture research cautions that students do not always use recordings strategically and that recordings are most effective when used as a supplement rather than a replacement for live sessions (Banerjee, 2021). The practical implication is that recordings need to be coupled with a learning activity that creates a reason to revisit content purposefully.

5.2. Zoom mediation and the social presence trade-off

The survey indicates a clear preference for in-person engagement: two-thirds of respondents reported engaging more in person than via Zoom. Responses also indicate weaker connection with the remote guest lecturer compared with in-person guest lectures.

This finding is consistent with evidence that social presence is strongly related to perceived learning and satisfaction in mediated environments (Richardson et al., 2017). In this case, the trade-off emerged even though Q&A was actively moderated and questions from both in-room and online audiences were integrated. The implication is that moderation is necessary, but may not be sufficient: interaction has to be designed as a first-order element, especially when the guest speaker is remote. In large classes, relationships and peer connection do not scale automatically, they have to be built into the learning design (Felten & Farrell, 2024). This point is consistent with HyFlex research showing that flexibility across participation modes does not in itself guarantee an equivalent learning experience; rather, engagement depends on how interaction, access, and classroom connectedness are designed and supported across modalities (Barr & Luo, 2025; Yang et al., 2025). For guest lectures, three design moves follow:

1. Interleave interaction: short question windows during the session rather than end-loaded Q&A.
2. Increase reciprocal visibility: explicitly surface online participation in the room and ensure that online participants can follow in-room interaction as more than a hidden backchannel.
3. Use structured prompts: brief polls or “type one takeaway/question now” moments that require participation and increase immediacy.

These moves can be implemented without materially increasing staff workload, which matters in large-class contexts.

5.3. AI transcripts and summary notes

More than half of respondents rated AI transcripts and summary notes as very or extremely useful, and almost half reported that transcripts strongly supported their ability to review and reflect. This suggests that AI artefacts can provide useful post-lecture support, particularly when guest lecture content is example-rich and delivered at pace. However, nearly a quarter of respondents were unaware of or did not use the transcripts/notes. This is an important practical finding, availability does not guarantee uptake. At large-cohort scale, resource availability alone is insufficient. When students are navigating a shared virtual learning environment, several recorded sessions, and multiple module demands, teachers cannot rely on informal reminders or ad hoc clarification to communicate why a resource matters. Resources therefore need explicit signposting, location cues, and a stated learning purpose, for example whether a transcript is intended for revision, retrieval of examples, or reflective writing. Smaller cohorts can also face overload, but scale reduces opportunities for individual prompting and makes uptake more uneven unless scaffolding is built into the design.

A further issue concerns trust and accuracy. The transcripts and notes were lightly edited to correct obvious errors. This is a pragmatic response to evidence that ASR accuracy varies across conditions and that streaming contexts can reduce reliability (Kuhn et al., 2023). Importantly, the aim is to provide sufficient reliability to support search, retrieval, and reflection, rather than perfect transcription. A related issue concerns learning behaviour. Students' endorsement of transcripts as potential substitutes for note-taking is understandable: transcripts reduce the "capture burden." Yet evidence on note-taking suggests that conceptual learning may be weaker when note-taking becomes verbatim transcription rather than generative processing (Mueller & Oppenheimer, 2014). Recent critique of AI summarisation similarly warns that such tools may encourage more superficial engagement with source material when summaries are used in place of reading or active processing (Corbin & Walton, 2025). The pedagogical implication is therefore to redesign note-taking rather than discourage it. In a large class, staff can prompt students to record one key concept, one guest-lecture example, and one question or implication during the live session, then use the transcript afterwards to verify wording or retrieve detail. Framed in this way, transcripts support engagement rather than replace it.

5.4. Reflection integration

The end-of-module free reflection was designed not only to be low-stakes and feasible at cohort scale, but also to provide a structured post-event scaffold in a large class where

spontaneous debriefing and individual follow-up cannot be assumed. Evidence on reflective practice suggests that reflection can support professional learning, but its educational value depends on the way reflective activity is designed and scaffolded (Mann et al., 2009). In a large class, a practical way to increase reflective specificity without increasing marking burden is to ask students to ground reflection in a small number of concrete references. For example, students can be asked to:

- reference one concrete example from a guest lecture (e.g., a transcript excerpt or timestamp),
- link it to a module concept (e.g., stakeholder management, governance, risk, leadership, delivery approach), and
- articulate one transferable lesson for future practice.

This integrates the AI transcript into learning as a scaffold, while also reducing the temptation to produce generic reflections.

5.5. Implications for large-class practice

Based on the design and descriptive findings, five implications are proposed:

- Treat guest lectures as a three-phase design: access before, interaction during, and consolidation after.
- Design interaction intentionally for remote speakers: moderation plus interleaved prompts and visible cross-audience pathways.
- Onboard students to transcripts and AI notes: where they are, how to use them, and what their limits are.
- Use minimal human oversight strategically: light editing increases usability; transparency maintains trust.
- Connect transcripts to reflection: asking students to reference specific examples promotes deeper processing without unsustainable workload.

These design choices position guest lectures as reusable and more inclusive learning opportunities within large-class teaching.

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